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DEMOCRACY AND THE POLITICAL SYSTEM IN ROMANIA: EVIDENCE FROM THE EUROPEAN VALUES SURVEY

Introduction. The collapse of the communist bloc in 1989 marked the end of communist ideology and the entry of Central and Eastern European states onto the path of capitalist modernization. In Romania, the process of change has been constantly redefined in the last 36 years, giving rise to a society that oscillates between tradition and modernization.

The post-communist period in Romania is marked by a series of problems whose origins can be traced back to the communist period, to the economic, social and cultural policies promoted after World War II. One of the dilemmas that Romanian society faces is related to the different way generations born before and after 1989 relate to the multiparty political system in Romania and to the degree of trust that Romanian citizens have in Romanian democracy. The present study aims to analyze the way in which generations before and after 1989 relate to these problems.

The lack of multiparty system, a phenomenon characteristic of totalitarian societies, and not experiencing the „multiparty competition” directly influence the opinion on politics and democracy (Pop-Eleches and Tucker, 2014). For Romanians born during the communist period, the notion of a political party was identical to that of the communist party, that is, a single political formation that monopolized the entire political spectrum. The communist legacy has negatively influenced residents' perceptions of the political system in the countries of the former communist bloc. (Pop-Eleches and Tucker, 2011). Another analysis was conducted by Pop-Eleches and Tucker (2014) who analysed “the effect of individual exposure to [communism](#) on support for democracy and capitalism”. The population’s evaluation of democracy depends both on political and democratic knowledge and on democratic values in that country (Carsten Wegscheider and Toralf Stark, 2020). „The more authoritarian the regime, the more negative the evaluation of democratic performance by people who are more knowledgeable about democracy. In contrast, (...) the more democratic the regime, the more positive is the assessment of

democracy by people with high democratic knowledge” (Carsten Wegscheider and Toralf Stark, 2020).

Opinions on democracy and their relationship with political systems among citizens worldwide were studied by Błaszczewski and Paweł Nowakowski (2025) based on data from World Value Survey. Valgarðsson and Devine (2022) analysed the dynamics and consistency of “satisfaction with democracy”. Their results showed that „*trends* and between-country differences in democratic satisfaction are similar”. [Marta Kołczyńska](#) (2020) studied the relationship between education, democratic values, and political trust. „The results show that democratic values partially mediate the effect of education on political trust, but the magnitude of this effect depends on the level of democracy” ([Marta Kołczyńska](#), 2020).

Data and Method. Data used in this research are from European Values Study, which is a cross-national and longitudinal survey on European adult population regarding their values, opinions and beliefs about family, society, politics, work, and religion. We analysed data from a representative random sample of individuals of 18 years old and older in Romania, from fifth wave (2017-2020). Variables included in the analysis are:

- *Confidence in Political Parties* with a 4-point scale as follows: 1 = "A great deal"; 2 = "Quite a lot" ; 3 = "Not very much" ; 4 = "None at all"
- *Satisfaction with the political system*, measured on a 10 point scale ranging from 1 = "Not satisfied at all" to 10 = "Completely satisfied".
- *Political system: Having a democratic political system* with 4 points scale, as follows: 1 = Very good; 2=Fairly good; 3=Fairly bad; 4= Very bad.
- *Importance of democracy* measured on a 10 point scale ranging from 1 = " Not at all important " to 10 = " Absolutely important ".

Results. Descriptive statistics indicate important differences in opinions on the democratic political system. Although the two groups of respondents have relatively similar opinions on the democratic political system - 92% of those born before 1989 and 86.2% of those born after 1989 reported a good and very good opinion - the Gamma coefficient value of 0.152 reflects a direct and statistically significant association (sig = 0.002) but low relationship between opinions on the political system and the two groups of Romanian respondents.

51.5% of the Romanian respondents born before 1989 and 55.4% Romanian respondents born after 1989 have no confidence in political parties. Moreover, the relationship between confidence in political parties and the two groups is weak and not statistically significant. Therefore, we can say that the opinion towards political systems is similar for the two groups. Political multi-partyism is an idea accepted by both groups of Romanian respondents.

The opinion on satisfaction with the political system has a large variation across Romanian respondents, with a coefficient of variation of 0.67. The opinion on importance of democracy has a small variation across Romanian respondents, with a coefficient of variation of 0.27. Since democracy is an accepted and recognized concept among both groups, the variation is small.

There are significant differences between the two groups of individuals regarding their opinions on the importance of democracy ($t = 3.037$, sig = 0.002,

95% CI: 0.133; 0.620). The effect size, Cohen's $D = 0.157$, means a small difference between the two groups of respondents. Democracy is perceived differently by the two groups, due to the different political experiences they have had.

There are no significant differences between the two groups of respondents regarding the opinions on satisfaction with the political system ($t = -0.178$, $sig = 0.473$). Both groups agree that the democratic political system is the most suitable for today's Romania.

Conclusions. The results provide evidence of differences in opinions on democracy and the political system. The differences in opinions between the two groups are generated by different political experiences but also by the indoctrination which people born and who lived before 1989 were subjected to. The differences are due to the exposure of the pre-1989 generations to the communist regime.

Future research will be more complex and will include more age groups in order to refine the results regarding the population's opinion on the political system and democracy while better reflecting the influence of communist indoctrination on the population.

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